

Study of cationic polyelectrolyte adsorption onto quartz surface using an electrode-separated piezoelectric sensor

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The adsorption of a cationic polyelectrolyte onto quartz surface from aqueous solution has been studied using an electrode-separated piezoelectric sensor (ESPS). The adsorption process has been monitored *in situ* in Britton-Robinson buffer at different concentrations of polyelectrolyte. The adsorption mechanism is described. The adsorption density is influenced by pH and electrolyte concentration.

Piezoelectric quartz crystal sensor (PQCS) is widely used as a microgravimetric tool *in situ* for studying adsorption process¹. The PQCS technique, capable of measuring as small as nanogram mass change on the quartz surface, provides high sensitivity and simple relationship between the mass load and the frequency change of the quartz crystal^{2,3}. ESPS possesses the excellent qualities of the PQCS and it is convenient to investigate the mass change on the surface of the quartz from solution⁴. The frequency change of quartz crystal due to the mass load is predicted by Sauerbrey equation,

$$\Delta F = -2.26 \times 10^{-6} F_0^2 \Delta m/A \quad (1)$$

where ΔF is the frequency change resulting from the mass load Δm on the quartz with an adsorption area of A and fundamental frequency of F_0 . Eqn. (1) is applicable with the assumption that the adsorption material is rigidly attached to the crystal surface and has negligible thickness compared to the crystal itself². It has already been demonstrated⁵ that Langmuir-Blodgett multilayers as well as polymer films with a thickness up to 30 nm can be considered as being rigidly attached to the crystal surface. Thus it is safe to use Sauerbrey equation to determine the polyelectrolyte adsorption density on the crystal surface in this experiment.

High molecular weight polyelectrolytes are commonly used as flocculants in many industrial processes⁶. It is of interest to determine the adsorption density of polyelectrolyte on the surface of the substrate and understand the adsorption mechanism. Poly(dimethyldiallylammonium chloride) (PDDAC), a flocculent, and used as a cationic polyelectrolyte here, can be adsorbed on the anionic quartz surface. The adsorption amount can be detected from the frequency change of the ESPS due to the mass change of PDDAC on the quartz surface.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption process of PDDAC on the crystal surface : At pH >3, the quartz surface is negatively charged due to the hydroxyl groups on the silicon dioxide and can adsorb cationic polyelectrolyte. The adsorption of polyelectrolyte on an oppositely charged surface is of the high-affinity type⁷. The relationship between adsorption density and frequency change can be derived from Sauerbrey equation,

$$\Gamma = \Delta m/A = \Delta F / -2.26 \times 10^{-6} F_0^2 \quad (2)$$

where Γ is the adsorption density in g cm^{-2} .

It has been found that liquid properties such as viscosity, density, conductivity and dielectric constant can also lead to frequency change of the crystal⁸. In our experiment, viscosity, density and dielectric constant are roughly constant since the concentration of the polyelectrolyte in B-R buffer was about $1.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. It was quite dilute and it was reasonable to neglect the small variation in viscosity, density and dielectric constant. In order to determine the adsorption density of the polyelectrolyte, it was also desirable to keep the conductivity of the stock solution to be equal to that of the B-R buffer, adjusting with concentrated KCl solution. After such treatment, the frequency change in our experiment can be considered exclusively the result of the polyelectrolyte adsorption on the crystal surface.

As shown in Fig. 1, the frequency change due to the adsorption of PDDAC on the oppositely charged quartz surface and the corresponding adsorption density were monitored as a function of time at various concentrations of PDDAC. It can be seen that the adsorption rate decreased with time and finally remained unchanged. This is obvious because with the progress of adsorption, both the adsorption sites of the quartz surface and the concentration of PDDAC in the solution were decreasing. The initial

rate of adsorption increased and the time required to reach equilibrium decreased with the concentration of PDDAC.

Fig. 1. Adsorption of PDDAC on quartz surface as a function of time in B-R buffer at pH 8.3: (1) 7.2×10^{-6} , (2) 1.8×10^{-5} , (3) 3.6×10^{-5} , (4) 7.2×10^{-5} .

In spite of different concentrations of PDDAC, the adsorption maxima were the same for each concentration. It seems likely that the adsorption amount is limited by the crystal when the concentration of PDDAC is relatively high compared to the adsorption sites of the quartz surface. Only the adsorption rate is dependent on the concentration.

Adsorption mechanism of PDDAC on the quartz surface : The adsorption isotherm (Fig. 2) was obtained through stepwise addition of PDDAC. After addition of certain amount of PDDAC, the frequency change due to adsorption of PDDAC was recorded during the same adsorption period of 2 min. The adsorption density was roughly proportional to the PDDAC concentration when the concentration of PDDAC was relatively low. When the

Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherm of PDDAC in B-R buffer at pH 8.3; $C_{\text{PDDAC}} = 3.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

PDDAC concentration was greater than $2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, the adsorption isotherm became flat. This indicates that the adsorption has become saturated on the quartz surface and an adsorption-desorption equilibrium has been built up.

The adsorption of polyelectrolyte on an oppositely charged surface is essentially an ion exchange process at low ionic strength. The charged segments of PDDAC replace $\text{Na}^+(\text{K}^+)$ on the quartz surface and attach the polyelectrolyte onto the surface through electrostatic interaction. Also the hydrophobic interaction, one of the surface characteristics of polyelectrolytes, of the backbone may contribute to the affinity of the adsorption. Compared to the adsorption layers of surfactants⁹, in which the surfactants orient themselves towards the solution and the first layer turns the quartz surface from hydrophilic to almost completely hydrophobic, the adsorbed polyelectrolytes lie flatly on the quartz surface although they may be linear, coiled or crossed and the adsorbed layer is a dilute phase with a large water content⁶. We can also expect that the thickness of the adsorbed layer of the polyelectrolytes is rather small taking the flat adsorption pattern of polyelectrolytes into consideration.

Effect of pH on the adsorption density : The effect of pH on the adsorption density is shown in Fig. 3. As pH of the solution increased, the adsorption density increased until it reached a maximum at pH 8.3, and then decreased. The increase in adsorption before pH 8.3 may be due to the increase of zeta potential of the quartz surface in the negative direction¹⁰. With the increasing basicity after pH 8.3, the decrease in the adsorption density may be caused by

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on the adsorption density of PDDAC in B-R buffer; $C_{\text{PDDAC}} = 3.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

the decreasing concentration of the PDDAC cation, since hydroxyl group combines with the cationic segment of PDDAC and quaternary ammonium is formed, which results in the decrease of the free cationic segments.

Effect of electrolyte concentration on the adsorption density : Fig. 4 shows the effect of electrolyte concentration, represented by conductivity in our experiment. With the increasing conductivity of the PDDAC solution, the adsorption density decreased. This is in agreement with the theory¹¹ and the experiment⁶, all of which presented that the adsorption of polyelectrolyte on flat smooth surfaces

decreases with electrolyte concentration. When the electrolyte concentration is increased, the cationic ions begin to compete successfully with polyelectrolyte for the adsorption sites on the quartz surface. The adsorbed polyelectrolyte layer becomes less dense and the desorp-

Fig. 4. Effect of electrolyte concentration on the adsorption density of PDDAC in B-R buffer at pH 8.3; $C_{\text{PDDAC}} = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

tion process proceeds when more ions replace the charged segments of the polyelectrolyte. And as a consequence, the adsorption density decreased.

Experimental

The construction of the ESPS device is shown in Fig. 5. An AT-cut bare quartz crystal with fundamental frequency of 1 MHz (Beijing 707 Manufactory, China) attached to the Neflon detection cell with silicone resin was derived by the oscillation circuit. Two platinum electrodes (area 1 cm^2) were separated from the crystal at a distance of 1 mm. The frequency of the crystal was monitored by a frequency counter (Shijiazhuang 4th Radio Factory, China). The detection cell was enclosed in a water thermostat, and the

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of ESPS device : (A) oscillation circuit, (B) frequency counter, (C) quartz crystal, (D₁) detection cell 1, (D₂) detection cell 2, (E) platinum electrode, (F) magnetic stirrer, (G) nefflon detection body.

solution was stirred by a magnetic stirrer. A DDS-11 conductivity meter (Shanghai 2nd Analytical Instruments Factory, China) was used to measure the conductivity. pHs-2

pH meter (Shanghai 2nd Analytical Instruments Factory, China) was used.

The stock solution of PDDAC ($4.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) was prepared in B-R buffer. Concentrated KCl solution was used to adjust conductivity of the solutions. B-R buffer was prepared by mixing 0.4 mol dm^{-3} orthophosphoric acid, acetic acid, boric acid and 0.2 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide.

Except PDDAC, all chemicals were of A.R. grade. All experiments were carried out at room temperature and triple-distilled water was used throughout.

Procedure : The quartz crystal was soaked at 80° in $\text{HCl (36\%)} / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{H}_2\text{O } 1 : 1 : 5$ (v/v/v), and at 80° in $\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O (25\%)} / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ $1 : 1 : 5$ (v/v/v) solutions for 5 min. Then at room temperature (25°) the crystal was rinsed with water for several times. The detection cell D₁ was filled 1 M KCl solution (10 ml) and cell D₂ with B-R buffer (25 ml). After stabilization for 20 min at room temperature, the frequency was recorded as F_1 , and the polyelectrolyte stock solution was injected in the B-R solution with a microsyringe. After the adsorption of PDDAC reached equilibrium, the frequency was recorded as F_2 and the frequency change was $\Delta F = F_2 - F_1$. The adsorption density was calculated according to Sauerbrey equation².

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